

The Impact Of The Corona Pandemic On Domestic Violence In Jordanian Society From The Point Of View Of The Husbands Themselves

Rihab Ahmad Bani Saeed

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 24, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 27, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Corona Pandemic, Domestic Violence, Jordanian Society, Husbands, The Family</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5806554</p>	<p><i>The study aimed to identify the impact of the Corona pandemic on domestic violence in Jordanian society from the point of view of the spouses themselves, the study relied on the descriptive analytical approach and a questionnaire was used to collect data and information, which included two dimensions, the first is the level of violence directed by the husband towards the wife, and the second dimension the level of violence directed by the wife towards the husband, in addition to the study of some social variables related to the study, the study sample consisted of (171) in Irbid Governorate in Jordan, the results showed that the relationship of domestic violence with the Corona pandemic directed by the husband towards the wife the overall average was in the rate of (2.42) with an average degree, while the general average of violence directed by the wife towards the husband was (2.25) with a low degree, the results indicated that there were no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) for the estimates of the study sample members for each of the sex, educational level, monthly income and family members, the researcher made a number of recommendations, including the establishment of family counseling centers and offices in order to guide husbands and families to resolve differences between them before they aggravate, especially in crises that society is going through.</i></p>

Introduction

The phenomenon of the crime of domestic violence extending since the existence of the human being on the earth changes and develops according to the change in the patterns of social, economic, political, cultural and psychological life in the society that the person passes through, knowing that it is present in all global societies, but it differs in the causes and factors leading to this phenomenon, which results in family disintegration, homelessness and deviation Children, and in 2019 new factors emerged that have increased the phenomenon of domestic violence in global societies, including the Jordanian society, and among these factors is the emergence of the Corona pandemic (coved-19) that swept the entire world and created many social, psychological, family, economic and health crises. Domestic violence was more affected by this pandemic, which led to a high rate of domestic violence in global societies, especially in Jordanian society, as a result of the comprehensive ban represented in closures, curfews and distance education from inside homes during the months The first of the year 2020 from the spread of the new Corona virus, which forced the countries of the world to close, apply home quarantine, stop all activities, close schools, universities, shops and cafes, lay off a large number of employees and workers in the private and government sectors, cut communication and direct social relations with people with each other for long periods (hdadin, 2020); Which led to an increase in psychological and social tensions and pressures and poor social and living conditions, and this was confirmed by the institutions related to the family, such as the Department of Family Protection and the Center for Strategic Studies at the University of Jordan, where it announced that the rate of domestic violence in Jordanian society in 2020 reached 33% during that pandemic, and this number Significant compared to 2019 (Center for Strategic Studies, 2020).

1. Study Problem:

This study is concerned with analyzing the phenomenon of domestic violence resulting from the spread of Covid-19 disease in global societies, which has caused harm to these societies as a result of the procedures preventive and curative measures taken by community governments in the application of domestic isolation and the closure of institutions in all its forms, which led to the creation of crises in all areas of life, including the family, which was subjected to psychological and social pressures and tensions and the loss of economic, food and health security resulting from family disintegration and violence, and this study also seeks to know the factors leading to violence. Families during the period of a comprehensive ban resulting from the Corona pandemic in Jordanian society by the spouses themselves.

2. Importance of studying:

This study theoretically seeks to know the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and measures and the preventive and curative measures taken by the governments of the countries of the world in implementing the comprehensive ban, especially in Jordanian society, which resulted in an increase in forms of domestic violence, whether verbal, physical, psychological or sexual by spouses, studies have proven that the year 2020 witnessed an increase in domestic violence and this is what Confirmed by the United Nations Women by studying the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic on gender equality in the Arab region. In practice, the results of this study may contribute to planning for the development of preventive, curative and guidance programs that benefit the family in order to reduce the negative effects on the family and society as a result of the spread of Covid-19. The importance of this study also emerges from the scarcity of studies and research related to the phenomenon of domestic violence linked to the spread of the coronavirus.

3. Study questions:

- What is the level of domestic violence from the husband's point of view towards his wife during the Corona pandemic?
- What is the level of domestic violence from the wife's point of view towards her husband during the Corona pandemic?
- Are there statistically significant differences in domestic violence during the Corona pandemic in light of some social and demographic variables?

4. Objectives of the study:

- Identifying the level of domestic violence from the husband's point of view towards his wife during the Corona pandemic.
- Identifying the level of domestic violence from the wife's point of view towards her husband during the Corona pandemic.
- Identifying the existence of statistically significant differences in domestic violence during the Corona pandemic in the light of some social and demographic variables.

5. Study Determinants:

- **Objective limit:** This research was limited to the impact of the Corona pandemic on domestic violence in Jordanian society from the point of view of the spouses themselves.
- **Spatial Limit:** This study was limited to the residents of Irbid Governorate.
- **Time limit:** The study was limited to the impact of the Corona pandemic on domestic violence from the point of view of the husbands themselves, during the year 2021.
- **Human Limit:** This study was limited to couples in Irbid Governorate.

6. Idiomatic and procedural concepts:

• **Domestic violence:** causing harm to members of the same family; Such as the husband's violence against his wife, the wife's violence against her husband, the violence of one or both parents towards the children, or the children's violence towards their parents, where this harm includes sexual assault, or the robbery of rights from their owners, and usually the abuser is the strongest party that is the perpetrator of violence against The abuser who represents the weaker party (Hussain, 2012).

• **Procedural:** behaviors outside the laws and regulations practiced by the husband or wife against the other, and it may be psychological, physical, social or economic behavior that hurts his feelings and loses his respect in society.

• **Corona pandemic:** It is an ongoing global pandemic of Corona virus disease caused by the Corona virus associated with severe acute respiratory syndrome and the outbreak of the disease for the first time in the city of Wuhan in China, then the World Health Organization announced the outbreak of the virus as a public health emergency of international concern, and confirmed the transformation of the outbreak to a pandemic. (WHO, 2020).

• **Corona pandemic procedurally:** an epidemic called the Corona virus that spread in China in 2019 and because of its severity, it has become a pandemic spreading in the world, resulting in many health, family, economic and social problems and still threatening the world's population.

7. Theoretical framework and previous studies

8.1 The relationship of the Corona pandemic to domestic violence

The phenomenon of domestic violence has been associated with man since the emergence of history, and that social, economic, family, cultural, and other areas of social change contributed to the rejection of domestic violence, and the community considered it social behaviors undesirable in society, such as the behavior of insults, beatings, threats, frustration, rape and others (Abu Hamari, 2018).

And due to the increase in the rates of violence against the family in recent years, whether globally or in Jordanian society, as the Corona virus (Covid-19) pandemic was a global epidemic phenomenon that contributed to the increase in violence and aggressive practices, domestic violence is defined as: "Any physical, psychological, or sexual assault or abuse by a family member, relatives, or workers within its scope, towards another individual, such as the wife, children, the elderly, and servants in particular, this includes a threat to

their life, their physical, mental, psychological and social health, their money and their honor” (Al-Yousef, 2005).

And that the form of domestic violence at the end of 2019 and the beginning of 2020 appeared in a new way as a result of the emergence of the Covid-2019 virus, which spread throughout the world and across continents, and it quickly spread to the World Health Organization declaring it a pandemic that must be addressed, and this resulted in a comprehensive ban represented in the closure of shops, government and private institutions, schools and universities, banning gathering, resulting in economic, social and psychological disturbances and pressures; Because of the disruption of all aspects of life in all countries of the world and the emergence of feelings of frustration and increased tension due to the circumstances experienced by the family, as the presence of family members inside the home for long periods may strain family relationships and increase psychological pressure between them, and this may turn into violence and psychological and social pressures between them for fear of infection or because of unfamiliar lifestyles caused by the Covid-2019 virus (Bradbury & Isham, 2020).

Despite the lack of studies that dealt with the relationship of disasters, crises and diseases to domestic violence, there are some researchers, such as (Wagers, 2020), he emphasized that the psychological structures of individuals are affected by times of crises and disasters, and remain firmly in their minds for a long time, causing them a state of confusion and trauma. the results of some research and studies related to risks, disasters and the spread of the COVID-19 epidemic have also been reached on the existence of a relationship between exposure to natural disasters, increasing rates of interpersonal violence, suicide, anger, cruelty, and aggressive practices within the family (Sehumaher, 2020), such as Alex and Jordan (Aiex& Jordan, 2020) study of natural disasters and their relationship to domestic violence.

8.2 Domestic violence in Jordan during the Corona pandemic

The spread of the Corona virus, Covid-19, made the countries of the world take measures and curative, preventive and developmental measures to limit the spread of this pathological phenomenon through the policy of social distancing taken by the countries of the world, especially the Jordanian society. Through the policy of physical distancing and a comprehensive ban, the crime of domestic violence against women, children and the entire family emerged. Where the Department of Family Protection of the Public Security Directorate in Jordan announced that the rate of domestic violence reached 33% during the Corona Covid-19 pandemic. And many countries of the world announced an increase in cases of domestic violence in light of this pandemic, especially the countries of the Middle East and North Africa, for example, in Kenya, cases of sexual assault and sexual crimes increased by more than 35% (United Nations Women, April, 2020). In Algeria, the incidence of female murder increased with a murder every 3-4 days (NGO, 2020) and in Egypt a survey was conducted on violence against women during the spread of COVID-19, and violence against women was 19% (UN Women, 2020). Jordanian society is indivisible from the countries of the world, as it considered that health and the citizen are above all considerations, especially on the economic situation by following the policy of physical distancing, comprehensive and home ban procedures, closing borders, land and air crossings, airports, and closing industrial activities the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has spread to many different sectors, represented by the following:

First: Psychological health: Psychological health specialists and those interested in this field have confirmed the high rates of anxiety, tension and psychological pressures due to quarantine, this may greatly affect mental health in society, especially women's health. A study by the Center for Strategic Studies at the University of Jordan showed that citizens look to the future with a non-positive view during the comprehensive ban, and that 32% were suffering from psychological pressure, depression and anxiety, and the percentage of females was 39% of severe psychological stress, compared to 35% of males, and one of the most prominent of these results was with regard to the psychological effects caused by the Corona pandemic, 66% of the citizens felt greatly anxious and afraid, 42% of the citizens were greatly affected psychologically, and 89% of the citizens felt sadness and frustration as a result of the closure of mosques, churches and related institutions this led to family quarrels and disputes (Economic and Social Council, 2020)

Second: economic effects: Many men and women working in the low-wage government and private sectors and small and medium enterprises have been affected, because of the Corona pandemic, which caused them Psychological health, material and economic illness, and health care due to their dismissal from work and the termination of their services for many families, especially working women. and their inability to provide the requirements of general needs, healthy nutrition and access to health care, knowing that Jordanian women occupy the third lowest participation in the labor force in the world at 14%, and this leads to a gender gap and increases the burden on women's activity in the Jordanian economy, and this situation will lead to aggravation. The challenges facing Jordanian women, it also suffers from many problems, which makes them more vulnerable to the effects of the economic shocks caused by the Corona pandemic, which has increased the burden on women's economic activity in Jordan, whether on their projects with high fragility, their employment opportunities, or their access to financing economic projects (projects with high fragility, 2020).

Third: Social Effects: Families before the COVID-19 pandemic were they obtain material, social and psychological support from relatives, friends, and some related institutions, whether government or private, but

after the closure and the comprehensive ban, they are no longer easily available to them and they cannot leave their homes, which has exacerbated the severity of the violence and the suffering to which family members are exposed, they were also affected as a result by social relations with others, and the relationship refers to almost non-existent ties with friends, family members, neighbors and co-workers, which led to isolation and depression (Al Harbi, 2020).

8.3 Types of domestic violence:

Violence may occur from the husband or one of the parents against the children, or vice versa, and it may be physical or moral violence, or both mean and there are forms of violence (Bin Said, 2018):

- Verbal or moral violence: It is the psychological harm that a person is exposed to and loses his sense of importance, as the father insults his wife or one of his children through humiliation, insult, repeated criticism, or the threat of divorce, and so on.
- Physical violence: It is the most frequent form of violence, such as beating by hand, using a sharp object, or pouring incendiary materials on the face, whether by the husband on the wife or vice versa, leaving psychological or social effects on the family.
- Sexual violence: Sexual harassment and assault are and are often the worst and most dangerous forms of domestic violence under threat of death or harm, or publishing explicit pictures that force him to engage in sexual acts contrary to social values whether male or female, rape is the most serious form of sexual assault in the family, and this falls under the category of violence and sexual harassment.
- Economic violence: the financial exploitation of a family member, such as appropriating the wife's money and benefiting from her income such as loans in order to buy real estate or cars, and so on, and this may psychologically, socially and economically affect the victim.

8.4 Effects of domestic violence:

The practices of forms of violence within the family may result in a number of effects, the most important of which are (Al-Saghir, 2012):

- The occurrence of divorce, family disintegration and deviations in the behavior of children.
- Lack of feelings of security and psychological and social security within family members.
- Juvenile delinquency, social isolation, bullying, homelessness, and disintegration in social relationships.
- The homelessness of children and their indulging in aggressive behaviors that violate the law and social values, such as drugs, drinking alcohol, theft, and others.

8. Previous studies

Study mesmar (2021) aimed to know the role of the Corona pandemic in perpetrating crimes of domestic violence in Jordanian society, and to explain the reasons behind its perpetration, the researcher used the descriptive analytical method, and the questionnaire as a tool for collecting information, and the study sample consisted of (500) respondents, the results of the study concluded that the dimension of social effects ranked first, and the dimension of economic effects ranked second, the results of the study also showed that the results of the study sample are positive and with a high degree towards all variables and dimensions of committing crimes of domestic violence, with an arithmetic mean (4.05) and a standard deviation (0.477), and the respondents' perceptions about the availability of the dimensions of domestic violence ranked first after psychological violence, and ranked second after physical violence. Study Xue et al (2020). entitled "The Hidden Reality of Domestic Violence During Covid 19", this study aimed to provide a broad analysis on domestic violence and the Covid 19 epidemic. The study used the analytical method in collecting and analyzing study data, where the data available on the social networking program Twitter was used, and more than one million tweets related to domestic violence and Covid 19 were analyzed, from April 12 to July 16, 2020. a machine learning approach was used, and prominent topics and tweets related to these topics were identified. The results of the study showed: an increase in the number of domestic violence cases and in the reception of emergency calls during the Covid 19 pandemic, It was found that the most common types of domestic violence during the pandemic were child abuse, domestic violence and sexual abuse, and that the most common forms of domestic violence were physical abuse, coercive control, and that the most vulnerable people to abuse were children and women. Amber study (2020), entitled "The Corona pandemic and its role in violence against children and women", this study aimed to know the reality of violence against women and children, and also aimed to know the impact of the social and economic situation on the increase in cases of violence, it also showed that the regional or global nature and the associated fear and uncertainty associated with epidemics are an enabling environment that may exacerbate or provoke various forms of violence, the results of the study showed that among the most important causes of domestic violence are: economic insecurity and pressures related to poverty, quarantine and social isolation, reduced availability of health services and access to first responders, temporary inability of women or children to escape abusers. Al-Harbi conducted (2020) This study aimed to identify domestic violence and its relationship to home quarantine, the study population was the city of Mecca Al-Mukarramah in Saudi Arabia, where the study sample amounted to (388) individuals the results concluded that there was no correlation between home quarantine and the phenomenon of domestic violence in Mecca Al Mukarramah, and the absence between home quarantine and the high rates of domestic violence in the study

community. Study Al-Amrawi (2020): This study aimed to identify the social distancing of the Covid-19 pandemic and the problem of violence in Algerian society, the researcher used the descriptive approach and distributed a questionnaire to a sample of (240) individuals. The results of the study showed that the stay of individuals with each other for long periods leads to disturbances within the family, such as lack of understanding and communication, weak family ties, and the emergence of address behaviors such as neglect, psychological and cursing and bullying. Study Alex et al. (2020): Entitled, The study aimed to identify staying at home in light of the Corona pandemic, represented by home quarantine and closures in the city of Dalay, Texas, USA, to increase rates of domestic violence, where the researcher used the comparison between domestic violence crime statistics for a period of 83 days before the imposition of home quarantine and closure, 35 days after the imposition of the closure, the results of the study revealed that there was an increase in the rates of domestic violence in the first two weeks after implementing the stay-at-home order, but then the rate of violence decreased. Study of the Directorate of Women, Gender and Development of the African Union Commission, (2020) This study aimed to identify the phenomenon of violence against women in Africa during the COVID-19 pandemic, the study, which was conducted in six countries in the Sahel region, showed that domestic violence, whether physical or spatial, increased by 40.6 before the Covid-19 crisis, reaching 52.2 percent during the pandemic, with an increase rate of 40.6 percent, 12%, where Chad, Senegal and Mali each registered increases of 30%, 14% and 10%, respectively, while Burkina Faso, Mauritania and Niger recorded 10%.

9.1 Commenting on previous studies:

By reviewing previous studies, whether local, Arab and international, it is clear that there is agreement in most of the results, as the study of Mismar (2020) and study (xu2020) focused on the spread of domestic violence during the Corona pandemic, as the Alex study (2020) focused on and the study of the Directorate of Women, Gender and Development of the African Union Commission (2020) to the exacerbation of the problem of domestic violence. Both Al-Amrawi (2020) and AMBER (2020) studies reviewed the social and economic causes leading to domestic violence, and that the current study has agreed with the studies mentioned, with the exception of the Harbi study (2020).

9. Method and Procedure

10.1 Study Methodology

The researcher followed the descriptive analytical approach, and this method was used to study the relationship of the Corona pandemic to domestic violence in Jordanian society during the period of the comprehensive ban; due to its suitability for this type of study.

10.2 study community

The study population consisted of the residents of Irbid Governorate, which numbered (2003,800) for the year 2021 AD.

10.3 Study sample

For the purposes of this study, the available sample was selected due to the conditions of the Corona pandemic and in compliance with the defense laws applied by the Jordanian government, and for this reason, technological techniques were used on the Internet, especially e-mail and social networking sites (WhatsApp, Facebook) and electronically packaged. The study sample consisted of (171) individuals from the Irbid governorate.

10.4 Study tool

The researcher used the questionnaire as a tool for collecting information and data related to this study; It fits with the nature of the study in terms of its objectives, methodology, and its ability to collect data, information and facts.

The questionnaire in its final form included (30) paragraphs, divided into two dimensions (the first dimension: husbands practice domestic violence against their wives by (15) paragraphs, the second dimension: wives practice domestic violence against their husbands by (15) paragraphs. the scale was designed with a five-step gradation (to a very large degree, to a large degree, to a medium degree, to a weak degree, to a very weak degree) and numerical scores were given, respectively: (5, 4, 3, 2, 1).

10.5 Instrument Scale Validity

To verify the validity of the study tool, the Face Validity method was adopted, and the tool was presented in its initial form to (12) specialized arbitrators in Jordanian universities, and their observations and opinions were taken about the validity of the paragraphs. It was also applied to an exploratory sample of (25) individuals from the study population.

10.6 Tool stability

To ensure the stability of the study tool, the equation of stability of the tool Cronbach Alpha was applied on all axes of the study tool and the tool as a whole. and the values of the internal consistency coefficients according to Cronbach's alpha equation for the tool as a whole amounted to (0.935), for the first dimension it amounted to (0.901), and for the second dimension it amounted to (0.936), and these values indicate the validity of the tool and its suitability for this study.

10.7 Statistical processing

The researcher used a set of statistical treatments that fit with the objectives of the study, where he used the Pearson correlation coefficient and Cronbach's α equation to verify its stability, and the frequencies and percentages were used to distribute the study sample according to its variables. Arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the responses of the sample members studying.

10. Analysis and discussion of the results

First: The social and demographic data of the study sample members.

Table 1:

Distribution of study sample members according to demographic variables

Variable	classification	Iteration	Percentage%
Sex	male	44	25.7
	female	127	74.3
	Total	171	100.0
Educational level	High school.	18	10.5
	diploma	14	8.2
	Bachelor	69	40.4
	Graduate	70	40.9
	Total	171	100%
Monthly income	Less than 500 dinars	59	34.5
	501-1000 dinars	64	37.4
	1001-1500 DINARS	18	10.5
	1501-2000 DINARS	11	6.4
	More than 2000 dinars	19	11.1
	Total	171	100.0
Nature of work	governmental	57	33.3
	Private sector	31	18.1
	Private business	19	11.1
	Unemployed	60	35.1
	Day laborer	4	2.3
	Total	171	100.0
Number of family members	Less than 3 people.	31	18.1
	3-5	88	51.5
	6-7	43	25.1
	More than 8.	9	5.3
	Total	171	100.0

Table No. (1) shows that the majority of the study sample members are females, with a percentage of (74.3%), while the percentage of males was (25.7%). it also shows the percentage of the study sample according to the educational level variable for the category (postgraduate studies) with a percentage of (40.9%), while the lowest percentage (8.2%) for the age group (diploma), while the percentage of the study sample according to the income variable for the category (600-600) 1000 dinars) was a percentage of (34.5%), while the lowest percentage (6.4%) was for the category of monthly income level (1501-2000 dinars), and the highest percentage of the distribution of the study sample members according to the variable nature of work for the category (governmental) reached a percentage of (33.3%). while the lowest percentage (2.3%) was for the category (day-worker), and the highest percentage was for the distribution of the study sample members according to the variable number of family members for the category (3-5) with a percentage of (51.5%), while the lowest percentage was (5.3%).) for a category (more than 8).

Second: The level of domestic violence from the husband's point of view towards the wife during the Corona pandemic

Table 2:

The values of arithmetic averages and standard deviations "level of domestic violence from the husband's point of view towards the wife during the Corona pandemic" and the dimension as a whole ranked downwards according to mathematical averages

Paragraph No.	Paragraphs	Arithmetic medium	Standard deviation	Rank	Degree of strength
1	Increased nervousness.	2.93	1.47	1	medium
2	Increased tension.	2.88	1.47	2	
3	Increased verbal altercations.	2.78	1.48	3	

4	Increased quarrels for reasons that are not important.	2.71	1.50	4	
5	Increased anger and blame for bouts of violence.	2.68	1.52	5	
6	Increase control and impose opinion on the other side.	2.61	1.50	6	
7	Increase the threat of departure and abdication of responsibilities.	2.45	1.52	7	
8	Increase your lack of security.	2.36	1.49	8	
9	Increase mockery and use obscene words.	2.33	1.45	9	
10	Increased threat of divorce.	2.22	1.50	10	
11	Increased threat of physical harm.	2.15	1.43	11	
12	Increase the prevention of communication with those close to even over the phone.	2.15	1.44	11	low
13	Increased physical beatings.	2.09	1.36	12	
14	Increased use of physical violence in front of children.	2.04	1.42	13	
15	Increase the threat of using sharp objects.	1.96	1.35	14	
Total dimension		2.42	1.31	-	medium

It appears from Table No. (2) that the general arithmetic average as a whole was (2.42), with a medium degree. Also, the arithmetic averages of paragraphs after violence directed by husbands towards their wives during the period of the comprehensive ban during the Corona pandemic ranged between (1.96 - 2.93) and came to a medium degree, except for (7) paragraphs that came at a low degree.

Third: The level of domestic violence from the wife's point of view towards her husband during the Corona pandemic

Table No. (3):

The values of the arithmetic means and standard deviations "the level of domestic violence from the point of view of the wife towards the husband during the Corona pandemic" and the dimension as a whole are ranked descending according to the arithmetic averages

Paragraph No.	Paragraphs	Arithmetic medium	Standard deviation	Rank	Level
1	Increased tension.	2.64	1.49	1	medium
2	Increased verbal altercations.	2.54	1.50	2	
3	Increased quarrels.	2.46	1.47	3	
4	Increasing the cyclostic and imposing opinion.	2.43	1.48	4	
5	increase indifference to the feelings of the other party.	2.43	1.49	5	
6	Increased anger and blame for bouts of violence.	2.42	1.49	6	

7	Increase the threat of departure and abdication of responsibilities.	2.40	1.51	7	low
8	Increase insult and mockery of your appearance, intelligence, or interests.	2.29	1.46	8	
9	Increase the divorce application.	2.24	1.53	9	
10	More than you call the other party's people bad.	2.22	1.45	10	
11	Increase the threat of harm with a sharp object.	2.20	1.39	11	
12	Increase the use of insults.	2.14	1.44	12	
13	Increased physical violence.	1.83	1.25	13	
14	increase bickering in front of the children.	1.77	1.31	14	
15	Increased death threat.	1.73	1.26	15	
Total dimension		2.25	1.29	-	

Show from the table Number (3) The general arithmetic average as a whole was (2.25) and at a low degree. Also, the arithmetic averages of the items after wives towards their husbands during the period of the comprehensive ban during the Corona pandemic ranged between (1.73-2.64) came to a medium degree, except for (8) items that came at a low degree.

Fourth: The statistically significant differences in domestic violence during the Corona pandemic in the light of some social and demographic variables

An independent sample t-test was applied according to the variable (gender, and one way ANOVA) according to the variables (educational level, monthly income, nature of work, number of family members). The results are presented below:

First: the gender variable

Table :4

Results of the t-test to detect the statistical differences between the average responses of the study sample members

Domain	Gender	No	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Degrees of freedom	Value	Level of significance
The violent dimension directed from the husband towards the wife	Male	44	2.64	1.33	170	1.798	0.073
	female	127	2.35	1.29			
	female	127	2.44	1.20			
The violent dimension directed by the wife towards the husband	Male	44	2.47	1.36	170	1.842	0.066
	female	127	2.17	1.25			
Scale as a whole	male	44	2.66	1.16	170	1.686	0.093
	female	127	2.41	1.18			

Shows from Table (4), the value (t) of the level of violence directed by the husband towards the wife according to the gender variable amounted to (1.798) and with statistical significance (0.073), which is a non-statistically

significant value at the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates of the sample members according to the gender variable.

The value (t) of the level of violence directed by the husband towards his wife according to the gender variable was (1.842) and with statistical significance (0.066), which is a non-statistically significant value at the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates of the sample members depending on the gender variable.

The value of (t) for the scale as a whole according to the gender variable amounted to (1.686) and with statistical significance (0.093), which is a non-statistically significant value at the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates of the sample members for the scale as a whole.

Second: Differences according to educational level

Table No. (5):

One way ANOVA to detect the differences of the relationship of the Corona pandemic to domestic violence in the Jordanian society during the period of the comprehensive ban according to the variable (educational level)

Domain	Variable educational level	No	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	F value	Degrees of freedom	Statistical significance
The violent dimension directed from the husband towards the wife	High school.	18	2.76	1.46	1.575	170	0.195
	diploma	14	2.24	1.26			
	Bachelor	69	2.50	1.38			
	Graduate	70	2.30	1.19			
The violent dimension directed by the wife towards marriage	High school.	18	2.74	1.53	2.688	170	0.046
	diploma	14	2.18	1.35			
	Bachelor	69	2.31	1.33			
	Graduate	70	2.08	1.13			
Scale as a whole	High school.	18	2.79	1.37	2.251	170	0.082
	diploma	14	2.43	1.24			
	Bachelor	69	2.58	1.21			
	Graduate	70	2.30	1.06			

It shows from Table No. (5) that the value of (F) for the level of violence directed by the husband towards his wife according to the educational level variable amounted to (1.575) and with a statistical significance (0.195), which is a non-statistically significant value at the significance level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$), which indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates of the sample members according to the educational level variable.

- The value of (F) for the level of violence directed by the wife towards the husband according to the educational level variable amounted to (2.688) and with statistical significance (0.046), which is a statistically significant value at the level of significance ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which indicates the existence of statistically significant differences and the presence of significant differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates of the sample members according to the educational level variable.

- The value of (F) for the scale as a whole according to the educational level variable amounted to (2.251) and with a statistical significance (0.082), which is a non-statistically significant value at the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates of the sample members for the scale as a whole depending on educational level variable.

Third: the differences according to the monthly income

Table No. (6):

One way ANOVA to detect the differences of the relationship of the Corona pandemic to domestic violence in the Jordanian society during the period of the comprehensive ban according to the variable (monthly income)

Domain	Monthly income	No	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	F value	Degrees of freedom	Statistical significance
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	variable						
The violent dimension directed from the husband towards the wife	Less than 500 dinars	59	2.65	1.37	1.668	170	0.157
	600 - 1000 dinars	64	2.38	1.25			
	1001 1500 dinars	18	2.15	1.27			
	1501 - 2000 DINARS	11	2.33	1.29			
	More than 2000 dinars	19	2.18	1.31			
The violent dimension directed by the wife towards the husband	Less than 500 dinars	59	2.60	1.39	4.400	170	0.002
	600 - 1000 dinars	64	2.16	1.18			
	1001 1500 dinars	18	2.00	1.26			
	1501 - 2000 DINARS	11	2.18	1.15			
	More than 2000 dinars	19	1.73	1.14			
Scale as a whole	Less than 500 dinars	59	2.79	1.26	4.362	170	0.002
	600 - 1000 dinars	64	2.41	1.12			
	1001 1500 dinars	18	2.24	1.10			
	1501 - 2000 DINARS	11	2.38	1.06			
	More than 2000 dinars	19	1.99	1.00			

It show from Table (6).

- The value of (F) for the level of violence directed by the husband towards the wife according to the monthly income variable amounted to (1.668) and with statistical significance (0.157), which is a non-statistically significant value at the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates. sample members.

- The value of (F) for the level of violence directed by the wife towards the husband according to the monthly income variable amounted to (4.400) and with statistical significance (0.002) which is a statistically significant value at the level of significance ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which indicates the existence of statistically significant differences and the presence of significant differences In the arithmetic averages of the estimates of the sample members.

- The value of (F) for the scale as a whole according to the monthly income variable amounted to (4,362) and with a statistical significance (0.002), which is a statistically significant value at the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which indicates the existence of statistically significant differences and the presence of differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates of individuals the sample.

Fourth: The differences according to the nature of the work

Table No. (7):

One way ANOVA to detect the differences of the relationship of the Corona pandemic to domestic violence in the Jordanian society during the period of the comprehensive ban according to the variable (nature of work)

Domain	Changing	No	Arithmetic	Standard	F value	Degrees of	Statistical
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	social status		average	deviation		freedom	significance
The violent dimension directed from the husband towards the wife	Governmental	57	2.42	1.31	0.576	170	0.680
	Private sector	31	2.32	1.24			
	Private business	19	2.27	1.41			
	Unemployed	60	2.49	1.29			
	Day laborer	4	2.90	1.56			
The violent dimension directed by the wife towards the husband	governmental	57	2.18	1.30	2.205	170	0.068
	Private sector	31	2.21	1.25			
	Private business	19	2.11	1.24			
	Unemployed	60	2.29	1.25			
	Day laborer	4	3.52	1.64			
Scale as a whole	governmental	57	2.47	1.16	1.277	170	0.279
	Private sector	31	2.36	1.15			
	Private business	19	2.29	1.31			
	Unemployed	60	2.55	1.13			
	Day laborer	4	3.21	1.57			

It show from Table No. (7)

- The value of (F) for the level of violence directed by the husband towards his wife according to the variable of the nature of work amounted to (0.576) and with statistical significance (0.680), which is a non-statistically significant value at the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates sample members.

- The value of (F) for the level of violence directed by the husband towards his wife according to the variable of the nature of work amounted to (2.205) and with statistical significance (0.068), which is a non-statistically significant value at the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates sample members.

- The value of (F) for the scale as a whole, according to the variable of the nature of work, amounted to (1.277), which is a non-statistically significant value at the level of significance ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates of the sample members for the scale.

Seventh: Differences according to the number of family members

Table No. (8):

One way ANOVA to detect the differences of the relationship of the Corona pandemic to domestic violence in the Jordanian society during the period of the comprehensive ban according to the variable (number of family members)

Domain	Variable number of family members	No	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	F value	Degrees of freedom	Statistical significance
The violent dimension directed from the husband towards the wife	Less than 3 people	31	2.53	1.21	0.676	170	0.567
	3-5	88	2.45	1.34			
	6-7	43	2.26	1.30			
	More than 8	9	2.55	1.35			
The violent dimension directed from the husband towards the wife	Less than 3 people	62	2.35	1.18	1.441	170	0.231
	3-5	88	2.33	1.30			
	6-7	86	2.00	1.28			
	More than 8	18	2.30	1.49			

Scale as a whole	Less than 3 people	62	2.62	1.08	1.530	170	0.207
	3-5	88	2.53	1.20			
	6-7	43	2.25	1.16			
	More than 8	9	2.54	1.28			

It show from Table No. (8)

- The value (F) of the level of violence directed by the husband towards the wife according to the variable number of family members amounted to (0.576) and with statistical significance (0.680), which is a non-statistically significant value at the level of significance ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages the estimates of the sample members.

- The value of (F) for the level of violence directed by the wife towards the husband according to the variable number of family members amounted to (2.205) and with statistical significance (0.068), which is a non-statistically significant value at the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages the estimates of the sample members.

- The value of (F) for the scale as a whole, according to the variable number of family members, amounted to (1.277), which is a non-statistically significant value at the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which indicates that there are no differences in arithmetic averages of the estimates of the sample members.

11. Discuss the results

The results showed that the arithmetic average of the level of violence directed by the husband towards his wife during the Corona pandemic amounted to (2.40) at a medium degree, where the items represented by nervousness, tension, verbal altercations, quarrels, anger, control and threat formed at a rate ranging (2.93-2.36). This confirms that the husband is the owner of authority and decision within the family, and that the Corona pandemic has played an important role in psychological pressures, quarrels, tension and nervousness among family members as a result of frustration and psychological pressures, not adapting to the comprehensive ban of the Corona pandemic.

As for the level of violence directed by the wife towards the husband, it reached a mean (2.25) with a low degree.

As for the social variables, the study showed that the sex variable as a whole amounted to (1.686) and with a statistical significance (0.093), which is a non-statistically significant value at the significance level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$), which indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates of the sample members, and this explains that the relationship of the Corona pandemic to domestic violence generally affected everyone without regard to gender.

As for the educational level as a whole, it amounted to (2.251) and with a statistical significance (0.082), which is a non-statistically significant value at the significance level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$). this indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates of the sample members. this result is attributed to the fact that the educational level of either the husband or the wife plays an important role in how to deal with social problems and domestic violence, as the low level of education may lead the husband and wife to lose the method of dialogue and discussion with each other, while the higher the educational level, the more it contributes to reducing domestic violence and the problems faced by the family.

As for the level of monthly income as a whole, it amounted to (4,362) and with a statistical significance (0.002), which is a statistically significant value at the significance level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$). this indicates that there are statistically significant differences and the presence of differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates of the sample members, and the differences were in favor of less than (500) dinars, with an arithmetic mean of (2.79). this is due to the repercussions of the Corona pandemic, which economically affected families with limited income, which led to an increase in domestic violence within the family due to the increase in the financial pressures that they are going through.

As for the nature of the work as a whole, it reached (1.277), which is a non-statistically significant value at the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$). this indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates of the sample members, and this is due to the fact that part of the workers were practicing their work from home, and this is due to the fact that work during the Corona period stopped at most segments of society.

As for the number of members of the sample as a whole, it reached (1.277), which is a non-statistically significant value at the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$). which indicates that there are no differences in the arithmetic averages of the estimates of the sample members, and this is due to the relationship of the Corona Covid-19 pandemic to domestic violence, which was not affected by the number of family members.

12. Recommendations

1- Establishing family counseling centers and offices in order to guide husbands and families in resolving disputes between them before they aggravate, especially in crises that society is going through.

2- Working to spread awareness and culture of family dialogue through various media messages to reduce the risks of domestic violence.

- 3- Work to find purposeful institutions and associations that support families in economic, psychological and social terms.
- 4- Activating the role of government institutions and civil society institutions in dealing with domestic violence in cases of emergency, disasters and crises experienced by society.

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Author Information

Rihab Ahmad Bani Saeed

Department of Social Sciences/ Ajloun University
College Balqa Applied University/ Jordan
